

Literature Review on Business Models in Developing Countries

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Abstract

The critical knowledge worker, which is urgently needed, will help build the user base. The exchange and transfer of information has never been possible in such an efficient and worldwide way as the Internet now makes possible. This article aims to do two different things. First, it offers a theoretical business model framework (BMF) aimed at helping small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) as well as inspired local entrepreneurs in developing countries understand the most important IT-related business issues. The Job Markets Fund (BMF) places particular emphasis on the prospects presented to companies operating in developing countries as a direct result of their use of information technology (IT), particularly their use of the internet (i.e., e-commerce). As a result, UNH should be implemented as a web-based platform that allows users to quickly learn about business prospects by navigating through ideas and relevant real-world examples (case studies). Currently, there are more than 20,000 international companies operating in emerging economies. The Economist reports that Western multinational companies expect 70% of their future growth to be in emerging markets, with 40% of this growth coming from China and India alone. . The World Bank ranked China 89th, Brazil 129th and India 133rd out of 183 countries in its 2010 Ease of Doing Business Index. The bank's findings were summarized in an article published in The Economist. The article states, "The only way companies can succeed in

these markets is to ruthlessly reduce costs and accept near-zero profit margins." Indeed, the difficulties are quite severe. On the face of it, nothing looks more mundane than a laundry room, a small refrigerator, or a money transfer service. However, if you take a closer look at the companies responsible for these services, you will discover the forefront of business model innovation. These innovative business initiatives shed light on a method that can help organizations recover from stagnant demand in their home markets, develop fresh and lucrative sources of income, and gain competitive advantage.

Keywords: *Literature Review on Developing Countries, Business Models, Business Models in Developing Countries, Developing Business Models*

1. Introduction

This may seem like an overly optimistic view, given the difficulties Western companies have had to enter emerging markets up to this point. However, we believe that the main reason for their failure is not because they cannot provide acceptable services, but because they misunderstand their business model. Many multinational companies are entering new territories by exporting only their own-grown product lines. They can get around by cutting costs by doing things like selling smaller quantities of products or using labor, materials, or other less expensive resources. Sometimes, in addition to hiring local country managers, they will develop and manufacture their products locally. However, the underlying profit formulas and business strategies have not changed; This means that these businesses will continue to focus most of their sales efforts on the highest income tiers that are not large enough to generate satisfactory returns in most emerging economies. Even the smartest of these startups sometimes lack a methodical procedure for redesigning their business model . This is one of the most common deficiencies. More than a decade has passed into the development of our business model innovation and implementation process. This has been achieved through research as well as our work in established and emerging markets. At the most basic level, the process can be divided into three phases as follows:

Find an important unmet need that the target customer has, draw a model that can meet that need commercially at a consumer-ready price. and then carefully run and refine the model, testing key assumptions and adjusting as you learn more . Start in the middle of it all. Established businesses looking to enter growing markets may be wise to model their approach around that of startups that see every market as unexplored:

They should focus on identifying unmet requirements or "tasks that need to be done". our language that can be satisfied profitably instead of looking for more channels for existing services. Jobs like this abound in emerging economies today. Even the most basic needs of their enormous population may not yet be met. In fact, the challenge lies in securing employment as well as choosing the projects that best suit your business's capabilities.

2. An Example for the World's Emerging Economies

There is a lot of work to be done in the developing economies of the world. Even the most basic needs of their enormous population may not yet be met. Numerous businesses had previously been taken over by the promise of profits that could be made by selling large volumes of low-quality goods and services to people in developing countries who were extremely poor. And in these markets, high-quality products and services are widely accessible to the extremely limited number of consumers who can afford them:

You can buy a Mercedes or a washing machine from anywhere in the world and stay in a Mercedes at the same time. Based on our previous work, we believe the huge mid-market between the two extremes is a much more productive place to start. Consumers in this region are not characterized by a particular income group, but by a common condition; this is as follows:

It will be to the advantage of businesses to develop new ways of doing business and new products and services to better meet the demands of customers at a more affordable price. Take the Indian

company Godrej & Boyce , which specializes in consumer durables . Godrej was founded in 1897 as a lock retailer; but the company has since grown into a manufacturer of a wide variety of products , including safes, hair dyes, refrigerators and washing machines. In the workshops we held with the senior management of the white goods department, the refrigerator market was identified as a sector with high potential:

Do they understand what customers are looking for in their purchase? No, simply put. A small team was tasked with conducting extensive observations, open-ended interviews, and video ethnography to shed light on the tasks to be completed for this underutilized market

The average monthly income of the semi-urban and rural residents the research team saw was between 5,000 and 8,000 rupees, the equivalent of about \$125 to \$200. These individuals often shared a one-room house with four or five members of their family and moved frequently. Unable to get standard refrigerators for their own homes, they gave up the common refrigerators that are often used. Researchers have observed, without exception, that there are only a few things inside them. His customers often went grocery shopping once a day and bought only a few servings of milk and vegetables at a time. Due to the unreliability of electricity, even the limited amount of food they tried to store was in danger of spoiling. Also, although they were concerned with maintaining a low temperature for their drinking water, the task of producing ice was not for these people to "rent" refrigerators. The team concluded that the most important thing for this group was being able to cut a meal in half while preserving leftovers and keeping drinks cooler than room temperature. This is a job that is distinctly different from what high-end refrigerators do; this is to keep copious quantities of perishable food on hand, whether cold or frozen.

3. Doing a Simpler Job

It should have been clear that there was no reason to spend a month's income on a conventional refrigerator and pay expensive fees for electricity to do a simpler job. And it should come as no

surprise that the answer is not a cheaper conventional refrigerator. This offered a chance to develop a fundamentally new product for the currently underserved middle market. It is much easier to communicate with those who have invested money to realize projects now. Focusing on this sector has two major benefits. First, it is easier to develop a solution to a problem that people are already trying to solve, than to generate enough customer demand for a product or service that does not yet exist. This is a lesson that sellers of purified water and other essential products or services learn with dismay. Secondly, it is much easier to communicate with those who are currently spending money to do their duties. Ratan That's what Tata has accomplished with the Nano, which retails for \$2500. He did not ask how I can persuade people who have never bought a car or other mobility to buy a car. He asked himself the question: " How can I find a better option for those who rent a motorcycle to transport their family?" The goal is to redirect current demand by offering a simple path from an unsatisfactory solution to a more acceptable one.

4. Offering Unique Benefits for Less Money

Your customer value proposition (CVP) should address a problem in a more effective, simple, accessible, or cost -effective way than alternatives. Only then will you be able to redirect the request. Our research has shown that accessibility and affordability are the two aspects of the customer value proposition (CVP) that are most important in developing countries. Let us look at each one in turn. Western businesses understand they need to develop lower-cost goods to compete in developing countries; however, they often limit themselves to giving less at a lower price. For example, in 2001, a bottle of Coke containing three hundred milliliters cost ten rupees, which is equivalent to an average daily income, a luxury the company claims only four percent of the population can afford. To appeal to the remaining 96% of consumers, Coca-Cola produced a 200-milliliter bottle and cut the price in half. This move has helped the company cut margins and become more competitive with standard alternatives like lemonade and tea.

However, in our experience, a much more robust strategy for creating an affordable offering for emerging markets is to trade expensive features and functions that people do not need for cheaper ones they need. This is because people tend to need more features and functions than less expensive ones. To do this right, you need to have a noticeably clear grasp of the environment in which the product will be presented. This requires ideally collaborative fieldwork rather than purely observational in nature.

In any industry this is sound advice for the creation of new products. In fact, it can be applied both to domestic businesses operating close to the country, such as Godrej , and to Western companies competing in a foreign environment. The team at Godrej prototyped and built a refrigeration unit from the ground up and then took the steps by evaluating it with real customers. Later, in February 2008, more than six hundred women came together and participated in an event focused on co-creation in Osmanabad , in the Marathwada region of India. They worked on the first prototypes as well as many subsequent prototypes and collaborated with Godrej on every element of the product's design .

For example, they may learn how to improve the efficiency and productivity of their business processes, or they may understand how to reduce operating costs by reducing material, purchasing and transaction costs, resulting in lower prices for intermediate and finished products. This tool allows them to do any of these things. Finally, they must be aware of how to increase the quality of the information they use to increase the value of the products they produce.

In summary:

- 1. Understanding the business challenges presented by the Information Society in the context of developing countries*
- 2. Understanding the interconnection between these business challenges, information and communication technologies, and the Internet in developing countries.*
- 3. Obtaining case studies highlighting the business challenges of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in developing countries and the application and use of information and*

communication technology as described above This document is divided into four sections for your convenience.

4. Architecture of the Business Model

In the context of the business model, we understand nothing more than a company's architecture and network of partners to generate, market and deliver value and relationship capital to one or more customer categories to generate revenue streams. In conclusion, the architecture of our business model consists of four main components.

- (1) Goods and services provided by a company that the consumer considers to be of significant value and for which the customer is willing to pay. The development of information and communication technologies has theoretically made it possible for businesses in less developed countries to access new markets for their goods and services.
- (2) capital a company develops and maintains with its customers to gain customer satisfaction, earn their trust, and generate long-term revenue streams . This component is especially important for businesses operating in export markets around the world.
- (3) Infrastructure and network of partners necessary to create value and positively connect with the consumer. And last, but certainly not least, a business model
- (4) It includes financial features that can be found in the previous three components, such as cost and revenue structures. This is the final component of a business model.

5. In Product Design

Innovation A company should ask itself what kind of business it wants to run, what kind of product innovation it wants to offer, and what value proposition it wants to offer customers. The company must determine whether the uniqueness of its value proposition is sufficient to ensure its continued existence and long-term development. The company must first identify the type of customer it plans to serve, and then decide whether to develop these competencies internally or contractually to successfully deliver the promised value.

6. Value Proposition

This component defines the benefits a company provides to a particular category of its ideal customers. The use of information and communication technologies has a significant impact on the development of new ways to generate and distribute value for businesses, especially in developing countries. These businesses enjoy significant cost benefits, such as low labor costs, but did not have effective access to global markets before the advent of the Internet. This prevented them from taking full advantage of the cost benefits. The use of information and communication technologies has significantly reduced transaction costs within organizations, between business partners and in marketing to consumers.

digital Opportunity According to research published by the Initiative in 2001, local artisans can now get 95% of the selling price of their products, compared to just 10% in the past. On the Internet, you can find several remarkably similar efforts that give locals the chance to sell their traditional crafts and agricultural products worldwide.

On the other hand, we can also see re-mediation because of the use of ICT. Alibaba.com, a popular Chinese website, is an example of a platform that connects customers in other countries with Chinese manufacturers and wholesalers. This is of immense help to Chinese manufacturers, many of whom have limited understanding of how to target foreign export markets. Another important aspect of the value proposition is the differentiation of products through innovation. This indicates that a company offers either completely new goods or services or innovative products or services

that complement existing offerings. Due to the prevalence of the Internet, businesses in less developed countries are now able to offer services such as electronic transcription and editing. A company obtains an audio file using the internet, cuts it apart, and then has many of its simultaneous workers completely format the audio file. The electronic document can be submitted again the next day. In North America, the cost for an hour of recording ranges from \$60 to \$100 per hour, which is equivalent to about five to six pages of written content [Rostenne , 2000]. Customization is another way information and communication technology can help differentiate products. Through the customization process [Piller et al., 2000], businesses can provide value tailored to meet the needs of a particular consumer. Small businesses in developing countries have a significant advantage in the market if they provide low-cost individualized services or goods that can be handmade and modified to the customer's specifications. According to " The Economist, 2000," the Internet enables a tailor in Shanghai to hand-make a suit for a customer in Boston, and FedEx takes over the delivery of the finished product. A third type of value proposition is to provide a high degree of customer service as well as an exceptional encounter with customer connection, in addition to the actual product or service being sold. The use of information and communication technologies allows businesses to offer brand new value-added services that can be provided at no additional cost. Intended demographic. In most cases, a company will generate value for a particular category of customers. The essence of where the company competes and does not compete is captured by the definition of market scope [Hamel, 2000; Afuah & al. 2001] specifies which customers, which geographic locations, and which product sectors are considered.

Due to the growth of the internet, businesses in developing countries are now able to promote their products and services to whole new groups of consumers. When the leaders of Chincheros , a small town in Peru , collaborated with an export firm in 1996, they were able to use the internet to increase the hamlet's income fivefold, reaching US\$1,500 per month. " Digital Opportunity According to the Initiative , 2001, community-grown vegetables are now sold daily in New York City. Capabilities. A company must ensure it has a range of capabilities to deliver a value proposition to a variety of customers. These capabilities serve as the basis for value delivered. Infrastructure as well as information and communication technology infrastructure are extremely

important for businesses located in developing countries where it is not always up to standards and often costly.

Businesses engaged in activities such as online commerce need a functional coordination infrastructure to successfully deliver products to end customers.

7. Relations with Customers

Creating new customer connections in international market segments presents a wide range of new prospects for businesses located in developing countries, and ICT provides these businesses with these opportunities. These businesses can get a meaning for the customer's wishes, serve the customer directly, and establish a long-term connection with the consumer using ICT, especially the Internet. A company needs to collect and use information about its consumers to improve their shopping and transaction experiences. Export businesses in developing countries can build relationship capital with their customers, which was a much more challenging task in the past [Tapscott et al., 2000]. If companies in developing countries develop good customer relationships and use trust mechanisms, they can gain the loyalty of their customers and compete directly with companies in developed countries. 5 Information Element This component refers to all the information and information a company can obtain about its consumers that it can then use to its advantage to find new and lucrative business opportunities and customer groups and improve the quality of its connections.

This does not necessarily involve the installation and use of data warehouses and data mining, both of which are known for their relative complexity and prohibitive cost. The use of e-mail and online feedback forms are examples of low-cost information retrieval tactics that can be used thanks to advances in information and communication technology. But these insights are important, and they can be used everywhere in marketing and sales, especially for customer relationship management (CRM). This is what Hamel calls the "positive feedback effect" (Hamel, 2000). As a result, businesses can accelerate product innovation and develop their goods and services faster than their

competitors. This brings in more consumers, creating a virtuous cycle that benefits all involved. In addition to improving its products, a company that better understands its customers is in a better position to develop a personalized connection with each customer to meet their specific needs.

Having a clear privacy policy that the company adheres to and discusses with its customers is undoubtedly an essential component of a successful business. Providing services to the customer includes activities such as fulfillment, assistance, and management of customer relations (CRM). In underdeveloped countries, businesses often struggle with inadequate infrastructure services (other than those related to telecommunications), which is a major barrier to e-commerce. For example, due to the unreliability of postal systems in Latin America, costly courier services are needed to deliver goods purchased over the Internet [World Bank, 2001].

Accordingly, a company has a responsibility to accurately define fulfillment and support in relation to the way it enters the market and the way it reaches consumers [Hamel, 2000]. However, direct selling has the potential to increase profits to such an extent that higher coordination costs may be unnecessary. In Nepal, for example, yarn costs start at Rs 175 (\$3.80) for a full-pattern shawl in Dhaka, and the labor cost of the manufacturer is Rs 275; however, the shawl finally sells for Rs 5,250 in the United States or Europe [Goodman et al., 2001].

Opportunities may present themselves not only through direct selling but also through emerging Internet mediation services [Sarkar et al., 1995]. Available online at <http://www.africancrafts.com>, AfricanCraft.com is a website focused on bringing Africa's arts and crafts online. This website acts as a conduit for African artisanship by providing information about online businesses, artisans, artists, and designers in Africa, as well as creating online courses on topics such as paper weaving to the city. This exemplifies one of the most well-known and widely practiced features of e-commerce, which is the dissemination of information about goods and value-added services through a website. A company can quickly provide its consumer with a wide variety of essential information about items, prices, and availability of these products, or even provide personalized real-time information (e.g., delivery status, product lifecycle management) to the customer. The worsening export performance of African nations can be attributed to demand-side non-price

factors [Oshikoya et al., 1999]. This trend could be reversed if African countries started using the Internet as a source of marketing information on prices and for after-sales services and quality improvement. Faith and eternal devotion. Even though companies in poor countries can now access global markets thanks to the Internet, this does not mean that they can always make the most of the opportunities available to them. Establishing trust and confidence among customers is essential to the growth of a company's customer base and should receive special attention from that company to attract new customers. [Hamel, 2000] argues that in today's information society, the image of companies (also known as branding) is shifting towards relationship dynamics.

This means that the perception of a company is formed not only by the transactional but also by the emotional aspects of the interaction between the firm and the customer. Firms in emerging markets should educate and implement mechanisms to build trust in e-business environments such as virtual communities, a positive performance history, brokerage services or insurance in case of loss, third party [Hagel et al., 1997, verification and authorization and clear a privacy policy, Friedman, 2000]. [Hagel et al., 1997] Virtual communities are an example of a mechanism for building trust in e-business environments. [Hagel & al ., In some cases, actual participation may be required. Entrepreneurs in developing countries need to fully understand the complexity of the market to run successful ventures. These markets are in no way like hubs like Silicon Valley, and as a result the processes of designing, launching, and financing startups need to be rethought. Trying to copy the successful business ideas of wealthy nations is a typical tactic used in emerging markets. This is something we see happening repeatedly. Innovators, business owners and investors often have the misconception that the success of a company in each demographic will also be successful in the developing world, provided that certain cultural and operational adjustments are made to meet the constraints of underdeveloped markets. On the other hand, effective models are rarely caught in developing countries where they are the norm rather than the exception. The product, technology and model are all outstanding; product-market fit has been shown to be effective; however, the product does not reach the customer.

8. New Markets

involve capabilities that are highly specialized and multidisciplinary, with a methodology that creates key consumer research and ecosystems. In the developing world, it is not enough to simply identify the ideal market for the product. To reach the customer at the price point that will trigger the profitable consumption level, certain infrastructures must be established with the launch of a new product. This is necessary to generate income from the consumer. The massive Chinese e-commerce platform Alibaba set out to facilitate international trade in Chinese products. In addition, Alibaba founder Jack Ma saw that the growing middle class was willing to pay for the ease of access to a wide variety of things. Ma recognized the potential to concentrate on service, targeting non-consumption to gain access to things the Chinese had no chance to experience, and took advantage of this opportunity. On the other hand, the necessary infrastructure to maintain a platform of Alibaba scale was lacking. In China, there was a lack of reliable online payment infrastructure, poor broadband connectivity, and no means for merchandise merchants to highlight their products online. Alibaba knew that to deliver its primary offering to its customers, the company must first build the necessary infrastructure to support it. Alibaba is the source. Alibaba has developed the necessary business infrastructure to serve its online shopping customers. by bringing together a group of incredibly talented individuals from the fields of logistics, marketing, and finance. Alibaba has not only laid the foundations for e-commerce, but it has also set up a local services division that trains small and medium businesses on how to maximize the sales of their online businesses. As a result, users have been given better access to Alibaba's core e-commerce services. Alipay was founded in 2004 to solve the credibility crisis that plagued online payment systems. It was presented to allay their concerns about the possibility of paying online before customers saw the goods. Originally built for Alibaba's e-commerce firm, this payments "infrastructure" has become one of the world's largest unicorns, providing every conceivable financial service for China's huge population. Alibaba is the founder and CEO of Alibaba Group Holding Limited. Similar strategies are already being used by startups in Latin America. E-commerce and coordination businesses Mercado Libre and Rappi are trying to optimize the

infrastructure for online payments and deliveries by building urban coordination networks and combining user-to-user transfer payments and financial closed-loop systems.

When using this strategy to conduct interviews, business owners need to have a noticeably clear idea of what they want to achieve and prepare their speech in advance to make sure the goal is met from start to finish. The first thing to do is prepare for the session and determine the role each person will play in the interview. If everyone does their part, all data will be collected. Since consumers will feel more comfortable in such environments, they should also consider the fact that smaller groups are more successful. When they arrive for the interview, business owners are responsible for remembering that their customers have entered their homes and other personal spaces . Therefore, it is imperative to show respect and decency. They should begin by briefly introducing themselves and discussing the objectives of the sessions. The end user should be aware that from the start the kickoff is there to hear and learn from what entrepreneurs have to say. Finally, discourse must have a natural flow. Users should be able to tell the story and businesspeople should be aware that they need to follow the target as this interaction takes place. One piece of advice we give to business owners is likely to be information.

9. Conclusion

The process of digitization can be compared to the process of industrialization in terms of its effects on the economy and social institutions. Just as the industrial revolution placed machine power at the epicenter of the economy, the digital revolution has positioned digital intelligence as the industry's new pivot point. During the industrialization period, the factory served as the primary location for mechanized production, making it the most important type of economic organization. In the case of the digital age, it is the industry platforms that are responsible for reorganizing the entire economic activity in each industry based on digital intelligence derived from data. The term "e-commerce" hardly scratches the surface of what this phenomenon really means. The digital economy is characterized by digital intelligence services, especially as they are applied to the

management of industry-wide platforms. Startups in the tech sector represent a new wave of entrepreneurial activity that, if used correctly, has the potential to launch a highly productive digital economy and boost overall economic development. Start-ups, on the other hand, should be supported by policies that address structural issues such as the availability of capital, the development of appropriate technical and business skills, regulatory measures against monopolies and other anti-competitive behaviour, technology regulations such as interoperability . The IT-based economic phenomenon has evolved in three distinct phases, which are alternately represented by the IT/software, Internet, and digital industries. A distinction must be made between modern technology start - ups that provide essential technical services, which are now exclusively in the form of software as a service (SaaS), and those that digitally transform certain industry services. such as education, health, and agriculture, as well as shopping and transportation. This second type is what can be considered a digital start - up . Providing digital intelligence-related services based on the data they collect is at the core of their business strategy. There are two distinct categories of online companies. concentrates its efforts on a specific subset of the services market. These usually occur in a competitive market and characterized by an elevated level of innovation. The company's competitive advantage lies in its use of innovative technology. The second type is those that aim to control the digital platform or market of an entire industry. They are monopolistic because of how they are designed. Business models consist of collecting the data and digital intelligence of an entire industry for the sole purpose of using it in their own operations. Such firms often engage in the practice of suppressing (and/or co-selecting) inventions that have the potential to put themselves in direct competition with their customers. As this is currently the case, it is possible that the software and internet application layers of the digital economic framework would get along well, served by private businesses operating in a unified global market. More work is needed on this subject in the literature. (“Using Manure Solids as Bedding - Cornell University”)

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